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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“WHEN THE SUN WON'T SHOW UP FOR ME, I HOPE YOU WILL”

I always show up. I wake up, do my usual routine. It's mostly just me taking care of myself. In my free time I do my hobbies, playing, singing, and writing — sometimes I like to throw in activities that are not part of my usual routine too. My life is no better than anyone else, I just live and live and live every day, of each week, of each month, of every year.

But what if I don't always want to live?

I get up, but I don't always have the energy to make my bed. On some days, I don't bother getting up at all. I could go for hours on end just staring at the ceiling while rotting in bed. There are days when I feel guilty for eating. So much so that I look at myself in the mirror, feel disgusted, and deprive myself of the privilege of eating. Some days, I do nothing at all. I've been working so hard to be better and build myself up after I lost my sense of self a long time ago, but then suddenly it all just comes crashing down. I do not know why, I do not know what is wrong with me.

Those are the days when I'm lost, when all I hear is nothing but silence.

But, I hope to hear you.

When the silence becomes unbearable, when I begin to become lost, and when the sun no longer shows up for me, I hope you show up to hold my hand and take me exactly where home is. When my days start to become dark and quiet, I hope you will be there to love me loudly.

I am not a perfect person—there's no denying that. Nobody is. If I ever show you the side of me that I've never allowed anyone to see, I hope I never have to apologize for being the way I am. I hope you'll be able to love all of me despite my imperfections. I hope you show up to love me when I can no longer show up for myself.